

Do financial inclusion and financial efficiency play deterministic role for FDI in Road and Belt countries

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Abstract: The study's motivation is to evaluate the impacts of financial inclusion and financial efficiency on foreign Cash flows in the Road and Belts countries for the period spanning 1971-2019. The study applies several econometrical techniques, but the magnitudes of financial inclusion and financial efficiency on foreign cash flows have been detected by performing Autoregressive Distributed Lagged in panel form and Cross-sectional ARDL and directional causality assess by performing non-granger causality test. The panel root test ascertains variables are stationary in mixed order but not after the 2nd difference; cross-sectional dependency test established that units possess some common dynamic among them. The long-run association reveals the results of panel cointegration tests. The results of ARDL and CS-ARDL confirm a positive statistically significant influence running from financial inclusion to foreign cash flows in the form of remittances and FDI. However, the magnitudes of financial inclusion and financial efficiency on foreign cash flows are prominent in the long-run. The directional causality test ascertains the *feedback hypothesis* explaining the causal effects between financial inclusion and financial efficiency and remittance and financial inclusion and FDI.

Keywords: financial inclusion; financial efficiency; Remittances; FDI; ARDL; CS-ARDL; Road-Belts countries.

I. Background of the study

A day's almost everywhere efficient market and financial service with the right way to use financial activity make the entire financial works easy, thus creating mass area and hope for improving cross-border capital flow or foreign direct investment[1-3]. The reason why it influences the foreign cash flow much border way is the financial efficiency that prepares a clear picture of any financial data of any organization and financial activity[4, 5]. This easy access creates a general positive acceleration of all cross-border investors and investors at the domestic level. The performance of stock markets and the consistency of accounting data are crucial facets of international investment. Studies demonstrate that a robust capital system plays an important role in stimulating economic production, reducing transaction costs, and allocating resources effectively [6, 7].

Furthermore, The economic advantage of strong credit scores for a business is that it enhances external funding availability and increases the likelihood of getting investors' capital to invest in the company [8, 9].

Also, it boosts the growth of a country's economy by increasing the amount of foreign financing[10]. Studies have shown that a stable banking sector would play a major role in the development of commercial activities and the overall economic growth of the nation[11, 12]

Financial inclusion and financial efficiency work as key functions to improve cross-border cash flow [13, 14]. The cash flow relay on level of financial efficiency because the level of efficiency in financial pact attract the international investor and market, but also domestic level investor and other markets, if the efficiency level of any countries financial market looks high then the country can attract foreign cash flows optimistically[15]. It unveiled new insights regarding the pattern of the relationship between financial inclusions and cross-broader capital flows by incorporating positive[16]. Measures include financial reform, efficient financial intermediation, adaption and diffusion of financial technology, the transformation of financial assists and efficient mobilization of economic resources along with financial market development, also include that the factor works in global investor's mind to invest a host countries economy is that the position of economic condition, financial practice and financial market efficiency[17, 18]. The factor concludes that financial inclusion is in the progress of a well-developing economy[19].

One important aspect of this trend is the progress achieved in expanding bank branches and areas of coverage. More or less maximum key developed country always try to attract the foreign investment by ensuring the efficiency of the courtiers' financial transparency, the reason why they want the financial transparency, a various investor from a foreign country will expect detailed information of the market financial situation of the market the economic condition status of financial inclusion of the country that aspect works as a key moderating tool for foreign countries to establish their business in any other country. It is important to show the foreign direct investor or foreign company the diversification opportunity because the foreign company will ask for a diversified market if the risk arises from the market about their business. To gather all this information and economic conditions, the host country must ensure the financial inclusion level is satisfied enough to capture foreign direct investors' attention. Only the cross-border cash flow can develop differently. On the other hand, financial inclusion means easy access to all financial services, and monetary transactions rage in most. At the macro level, the economy's growth seems critical, reasoning the easy access to monetary tools management allows smooth partly consumption and built assets, thus eventually improving welfare at the individual level and expanding possibilities to overall economic growth.

The study aims to investigate the relationship between financial inclusions, financial efficiency and cross-border cash flow. How the financial inclusion works to raise the cross-border cash flows and the financial efficiency works to improve the foreign direct investment. This study shows how financial inclusion works to help in the rise of foreign cash flows. Also, refer that how financial efficiency helps to transparent exceed output rather than the input of any financial works. The entire relationship between financial inclusion and financial efficiency expresses positive change. If any country maintains financial efficiency and strong output transparency with any financial works, any FDI or foreign investor would like to invest. Thus create an improving cross-border cash flow as an investment in the country. Like financial efficiency, if financial inclusion is similarly high in any country, any foreign country will invest in a similar country. The foreign country expects an improving financial system with the maximum effort of financial output. The country with higher financial efficiency has a high efficacy rate than the then lowest financial efficient country; they will provide a higher rate of financial output in any investment, which is very interesting for the foreign investor.

Furthermore, those investments will work as a dynamic cash flow while the financial inclusion will be higher. The more uses of financial service, the more uses of monetary transaction. The monetary transaction can provide a higher rate of business activity than any foreign investor wants, so financial inclusion and financial efficiency work positively related to foreign cash flow.

II. Literature Review

Financial inclusion and foreign capital flows

The key factor in increasing any development in any countries economy, lies in foreign capital flows hand. Cross border cash flow has become a key integration to improve the financial segment according to the world economy. The cross-border cash flow plays a vital role in creating more industry service and financial affectivity and support the economy to emerge and provide sustainable growth in GDP and growth in international trade. The cross-border cash flows have a positive relationship with financial inclusion and financial efficiency.

In a study, [Toxopeus and Lensink \[20\]](#) show that financial inclusion positively impacts Cross border cash flows. Using IFM, World Bank statistic data on remittance and GLS for 2008 with 63 countries, the study revealed that the remittance is part of foreign cash flow or cross border cash flows. Furthermore, if financial inclusion occurs in a good manner, the remittance flow can also improve. He also indicated that financial inclusion helps the country spare more financial activity, thus helping the remittance provider in a broad way to send foreign cash. So improving financial inclusion means improving foreign cash flows in the country. [Qamruzzaman and Wei \[21\]](#) find applying the System GMM approach with 58 developing countries in 1993 – 2017 that a courtier key economic development function has hugely affected by foreign cash flow. To improve the cross-border cash flow country need to improve the financial inclusion, thus implies a positive relationship.

[Zwedu \[22\]](#) investigates by using financial stability and inclusive growth Model, BDY in 2010- 2013 time period of 593 banks. How enlarged accessibility to financial service leads to increased financial service, thus creating an opportunity to exceed more business and economic position of a country. What attracts the international investor and makes them invest in such a country where financial users are higher? He also includes a lack of financial inclusion, and the foreign cash flows do not improve the growth. [Sarma and Pais \[23\]](#) investigate using Empirical Analysis with 88 countries in 2010 that because of financial inclusion improvement, day-to-day financial activity and users of financial works increase, making the foreign cash flow much effective in the country, which is an indication of positive linkage. [Ramasamy and Yeung \[24\]](#) reveal by using GMM estimator with orthogonal deviations from 1988 to 2010 that the incensement of financial inclusion means the increment of financial users, more users mean more transaction and transaction are vastly related with business, thus makes a strong business environment statement to a foreign direct investment which will attract FDI and thus can improve the foreign cash flow which shows a positive linkage between financial inclusion and cross border cash flows.

In a study, [Bevan, Estrin \[25\]](#) investigate that by using Cross-Sectional Analysis in 1988-2004 with a panel of 16 EU countries, the rate of developed country whose financial inclusion rate is higher than other countries who do not practice financial inclusion. In that way, it has a down growth rate of foreign cash flow that does not practice financial inclusion or improves financial inclusion.

In another study, [Morgan and Pontines \[26\]](#) investigate by using system-GMM dynamic panel estimator in time of 2007-2014 with several banks in a various country that The finding revealed that the financial inclusion have a mutual reinforce relationship with financial stability and has a short time and limited availability thus raged the negative linkage between financial inclusion and foreign capital flow. In another study, [Singh and Zammit \[27\]](#) revealed by using the Financial stability and inclusive growth model in the time frame of 1990-2000 with a panel of 63 developing country that due to the rural poor and gender inequality, the FDI could affect practising financial inclusion thus the relation between the financial inclusion and foreign cash flow seems negative.

In another study Reichmann, Karadzic et al. (2003), by using ASPH, LABQ, PEXP during 2003 in Turkey the study include that the more financial inclusion does not affect the foreign cash flows instead of

these the financial status of the country could affect the FDI thus make the statement neutral. In another study, [Barrell and Pain \[28\]](#) investigate using System dynamics in 1991-1997 with a panel of 9 EU countries. The study shows that transfer of technology is related to financial inclusion risk, thus impacting cross-border cash flow, which indicates a negative relationship between them. Risk can occur with maximum financial inclusion uses that show that if the monetary transaction assessment is very much easy, the liquid cash problem can occur differently.

In a study, [Barajas, Steiner \[29\]](#) amplify by using the Descriptive approach, econometric analysis in the meantime of 1990-2000 in Colombia that Financial inclusion has a general financial development in cross border cash flow influence sector thus has a positive relationship between financial inclusion and cross border cash flows. In a study, [Bailliu \[30\]](#) finds, by using a dynamic panel-data methodology, an economic growth model during 1975-2000 with panel data for 40 developing countries Financial efficiency-related the firm's financial data. Improvement of financial efficiency means improving the FDI transparency thus has a positive linkage between financial efficiency and foreign cash flows.

In a study [Adeniyi, Ajide \[31\]](#) investigate by using FDI-growth, empirical analysis method during 1990-2015 with African sub counting countries the study considered types of situation in financial efficiency in different financial resistance have different role and impact across the country which can affect the cross border cash flow. The efficiency may affect the remittance due to and can create a negative linkage with cross-border cash flow.

In another study [Park and Song \[32\]](#) investigate by using a dynamic model during 1990-1996 with a panel of Korea, Thailand, Malaysia, and Indonesia that the inflow of foreign capital has been crucial to supporting a high rate of investment and output in Indonesia, Malaysia and Thailand. In fact, except Korea, it appears that all three East Asian countries are prepared to accept all types of foreign financing regardless of their maturities so long as foreign capital vastly depends on financial efficiency. In another study, [Soto \[33\]](#) investigate that by using growth regressions during 1986-2000 with a panel of 44 developing countries, both financial development and economic development depend on financial affectivity, which is positively related to foreign cash flows.

In another study, [Taylor and Sarno \[34\]](#) investigate using Error-correction models, 92. Counteraction technique during 1988-1997 with the United States to Latin American and Asian countries in developed countries the FDI is hard to find out the efficient way of the financial tool, thus creating a problem in foreign investor linkage negatively with financial efficiency, and foreign cash flows. In another study, [Nguyen \[35\]](#) investigate that financial efficiency and cross-border cash flow are positively related.

In a study [Sturm, Williams \[36\]](#) investigate by using the System dynamic method during 1998-2008 with a panel of efficiency of foreign banks in Australia study considered types of situation in financial efficiency in different financial resistance have different role and impact across the country which can affect the cross border cash flow. The efficiency may affect the remittance due to and can create a negative linkage with cross-border cash flow.

Summary literature Survey Financial Inclusion and foreign capital flows (FDI)

Authors	Period	Findings
Toxopeus and Lensink [20]	2008	The study concludes that financial inclusion has a positive impact on remittance development. Which, of course, mean's a positive linkage between financial inclusion and foreign cash flow.
Qamruzzaman and Wei [21]	1993-2017	The study revealed a positive linkage between financial inclusion and cross-border capital flows.
Morgan and Pontines [26]	2007-2014	The finding revealed that financial inclusion has a mutual reinforced relationship with financial stability and has a short period. Limited availability thus raged the negative linkage between financial inclusion and foreign capital flow.

Morgan and Pontines [37]	2017-2018	Shows the negative linkage between financial inclusion and foreign cash flows due to the new risk from specialized MFI's
Sarma and Pais [23]	2010	Study Contribute that financial inclusion is the main reason why the day-to-day financial uses increase and all sector improvement. It increases the foreign capital flows. Show a positive linkage.
Zweddu [22]	2010-2013	The study explores that due to a lack of financial inclusion, the foreign cash flow is not improving, indicating the positive relationship between financial inclusion and foreign cash flows.
Bruno and Shin [38]	2013	The research shows that the relationship between financial inclusion and cross-border cash flows is positive.
Sarma [39]	2006-2008	The finding is that Financial Inclusion is a key line to success of overall financial indexes and cross-border capital flows. So it also seems positively related.
Ackah and Asiamah [40]	2001-2016	The study includes the negative relationship between financial inclusion and foreign capital flow because of financial stability.
Ramasamy and Yeung [24]	1988-2010	The study shows that to improve the financial service, financial inclusion is mandatory through which FDI activity will increase, thus indicate the relation is positive
Bevan, Estrin [25]	1988-2004	The study shows that developed countries' financial inclusion rate and foreign Investment cash flow rate are higher. This indicates a positive relationship between financial inclusion and foreign cash flows.
Athreye and Kapur [41]	1993-2001	The study shows that the export ratio improved in practising financial inclusion, thus presenting a nominal positive relationship.
Mwilima and Institute [42]	1997-2003	Studyfinding suggests that the FDI rate fully depends on extended financial serv, which shows how a positive linkage between financial inclusion across-borderer cash flows.
Schoeman, NJ [43]	1995-2000	The finding reveals a definite positive linkage between FDI flows and financial inclusion.
Singh and Zammit [27]	1990-2000	Due to The Rural Poor and Gender Inequality, the FDI could affect practicing financial inclusion; thus, the relationship between financial inclusion and foreign cash flow seems negative.
Deichmann, Karidis [44]	2003 -2015	The study includes that more financial inclusion does not affect the foreign cash flows; instead of these, the country's financial status could affect the FDI, making the statement neutral.
Moshirian and Finance [45]	1991-2001	This study indicates that Promoting the Use of the Transaction Account is a challenge and makes financial inclusion negatively linked with cross-border cash flows.
Barrell and Pain [28]	1991-1997	The study shows that transfer of technology is related to financial inclusion risk, thus impacting cross-border cash flow, which indicates a negative relationship between them.
Ang [46]	1960-2008	The study revealed that financial inclusion improvement works a key role in improving cross-border cash flows. This means there is a positive relationship between financial inclusion and foreign cash flows.
Shahbaz and Rahman [47]	1971-2010	The study suggests that due to a lack of efficient financial inclusion, the Pakistan cross-border cash flow is not improving, thus showing

		a positive relationship between financial inclusion and foreign cash flows.
Goldberg [48]	1991-2004	Shows the negative linkage between financial inclusion and foreign cash flows due to the new risk from specialized MFI's
Botrić and Škuflić [49]	1990-2006	The study includes the negative relationship between financial inclusion and foreign capital flow because of financial stability.
Bailliu [30]	1975–2000	study shows that the iniquity of financial inclusion and linkage of a negative relationship with foreign capital flow
Kurtishi-Kastrati [50]	1998-2013	The finding is that Financial Inclusion is a key line to success of overall financial indexes and cross-border capital flows. So it also seems positively related.
Reisen and Soto [51]	1986–2001	The study shows that the export ratio improved in practicing financial inclusion, thus presenting a nominal positive relationship.
Brafu-Insaidoo and Biekpe [52]	1991-2014	The study indicates a positive linkage between the cross-border relationship and financial inclusion.
Alfaro [53]	1981-2003	The Financial inclusion development is inversely related with cross broader cash flow development
Khan [54]	1975-2007	The contribution of financial inclusion increases the foreign cash flows, thus mean a positive linkage.
Barajas, Steiner [29]	1990-2000	Financial inclusion has a general financial development in the cross-border cash flow influence sector, thus having a positive relationship between financial inclusion and cross-border cash flows.

Nexus between Financial efficiency and foreign capital flow

The role of financial efficiency is extensively investigated in the literature, such as economic growth [55], financial sector development [55], renewable energy consumption [56], foreign ownership, good governance [57].

Furthermore, the nexus between financial sector efficiency, especially the financial sector, impacts foreign investment in the form of long-run capital investment in the economy and establishes a positive association [55]. The rise of financial markets can be linked to market friction in the context of transaction and information costs. Moreover, financial intermediaries often play a role in reducing risks associated with savings and expenditure decisions. Finally, capital markets are supposed to lead to an optimal distribution of limited resources and positively affect economic development. The depth of the financial system characterized by financial produce diversification and pool serving propensity in society contributes to fostering and efficiently reallocating economic resources, thus stimulating domestic investment scope [58]. Reallocation of economic resources helps the economy achieve economic growth with economic growth, hence acting as a motivating factor in stimulating foreign investors.[6, 59, 60].

Financial intermediaries work effectively, thus improving economic growth and corporate governance[61]. Owing to the presence of business frictions such as high transaction rates and knowledge asymmetries, dispersed shareholders may be discouraged from exercising sufficient influence over company management. Through the proliferation and maturity of financial firms, financial resources' availability grows in quantity and efficiency, which encourages overall domestic investment, especially through foreign investors. However, over the past few decades, the view that financial progress is a primary determinant of economic growth has been questioned from a different dimension. First, reducing challenges with capital distribution would not inherently result in stronger economic development. Due to financial sector growth, the savings rate does not generally increase as anticipated. Lowering individuals' liquidity constraints by financial innovations may lower the savings rate by lowering disposable income

[62-64]. Second, The so-called 'demand-following hypothesis' is backed by various economists see [Ireland \[65\]](#); [Apergis, Filippidis \[66\]](#). According to this theory, the two trends' causality goes the other direction, namely from economic growth to financial development: people seek more and better financial services in the process of a - market, which stimulates financial development.

In a study [Lensink, Meesters \[67\]](#) gauge the nexus between banking sector efficiency and ownership status of foreign direct investment for 1993-2003. Study findings reveal that the host economy's institutional quality immensely relies on the contribution from foreign investment; moreover, in terms of association study revealed adverse impact running from foreign ownership to efficiency of the banking sector in the long-run. Thus, the study suggests that the mitigation of the structural gap between the host country's governmental institutions and the home country's financial sector would also reduce international bank inefficiency. Furthermore, [Berger, DeYoung \[68\]](#) domestic banks tend to be more effective than foreign banks from most foreign countries, and this is the case for just about half of all foreign countries. Domestic banks are equivalent to foreign banks' efficiency [[69](#), [70](#)]. So, in the homeworld, international vs. domestic ownership's relative success is determined by the circumstances in the host country[[71](#)].

Summary literature survey financial efficiency and foreign capital flows (FDI)

Authors	Period	Findings
Bailliu [30]	1975-2000	Financial efficiency-related the firm's financial data. Improvement of financial efficiency means improving the FDI transparency, thus has a positive linkage between financial efficiency and foreign cash flows.
Arcelus, Sharma [72]	1995-2005	Suggest that the cross-border cash flow can be increased if the financial efficiency can be increased.
Nguyen [35]	1982- 2000	Financial efficiency and cross-border cash flow are positively related.
Edwards [73]	1982-1990	Explore the role of financial efficiency inset the cross-border cash flow. Study shows financial efficiency is related positively to the improvement of cross border cash flow.
Coerdacier, Kollmann [74]	1990-2010	The study shows that financial efficiency works to increase the development of FDI.
Schnitzer [75]	195-2002	Financial efficiency does not affect the foreign currency flow.
Razin, Sadka [76]	1992-1998	Financial efficient means all data to set about financial works thus create a problem for the foreign company thus decrease the FDI. This indicates negative relation.
Adeniyi, Ajide [31]	1990-2015	This study considered types of financial efficiency in different financial resistance have different roles and impacts across countries, affecting the cross-border cash flow. The efficiency may affect the remittance due to and can create negative linkage with cross-border cash flow.
Ali and Journal [77]	1972-2014	In the short run, financial efficiency may negatively affect the FDI, but financial efficiency will positively cross-border cash flows in the long run.
Asongu [78]	1990-2014	The study implies that financial development can positively affect financial cross-border cash flow.

Soto [33]	1986-2000	Financial development and economic development depend on financial affectivity, which is positively related to foreign cash flows.
Park and Song [32]	1990-1996	The inflow of foreign capital has been crucial to supporting a high investment and output rate in Indonesia, Malaysia, and Thailand. In fact, except Korea, it appears that all three East Asian countries are prepared to accept all types of foreign financing regardless of their maturities so long as foreign capital vastly depends on financial efficiency.
Levine [79]	1992-2001	Better-developed banks and financial efficiency can bring long-term foreign cash flow related to financial efficiency and cross-border cash flow linked positive.
Taylor and Sarno [34]	1988-1997	In the matter of developed country the FDI it is hard to find out the efficient way of financial tool thus create problem in foreign investor linkage negatively with financial efficiency and foreign cash flow
Sturm, Williams [36]	1998-2008	profitability is not found to result in increased host nation efficiency, while parent credit rating effects are mixed it shows the neutral relationship between financial efficiency and crosses border cash flow
Azam and Gavrila [80]	1982-2014	It takes a huge effort to make financially efficient to satisfy the FD investment; thus country should use diversify method, which indicates the neutral relationship between financial efficiency and cross border cash flow
Errunza [81]	1985-2001	The large-scale market cannot be fully efficient in terms of financial fact, thus delaying the FDI; it can even cause cancelation with a mix-up, so the relationship between foreign cash flow and financial efficiency is negative.
Demirgüç-Kunt, Levine [82]	1992-1998	the paper includes the foreign invests increase when financial efficiency increases
Ang [46]	1960-2005	In Both cases, financial development and economic development depend on financial affectivity, which is positively related to foreign cash flows.
Shahbaz and Rahman [47]	1971-2010	The study suggests that the Pakistan government should undertake financial reforms to improve the domestic financial sector's efficiency, which will ultimately increase the FDI rate in the country indicate positively related.
Goldberg [48]	1991-2004	This paper reviews the main findings and policy themes of FDI research, focusing on the financial efficiency for emerging FDI improvement, thus indicating positive relation.
Von Hagen and Zhang [83]	1995-2014	In short-run financial efficiency may affect the FDI negatively, but in the long run, the financial efficiency will work positively with cross border cash flows
Ndikumana [84]	1990-2003	shows that the financial efficiency helps a country to increase the FDI, which indicates a positive linkage

Prasad, Rogoff [85]	1983-2005	Major factors that have compounded financial efficiency positively relate to the cross-border cash flow due to output is always greater in financial efficiency.
Taylor and Sarno [34]	1988-1997	Better-developed banks and financial efficiency can bring long term foreign cash flow the relation between financial efficiency and cross border cash flow linked positive importance than domestic factors in explaining the dynamics of bond flow
Sturm, Williams [36]	1998-2008	This study considered types of financial efficiency in different financial resistance have different roles and impacts across countries, affecting the cross-border cash flow. The efficiency may affect the remittance due to and can create negative linkage with cross-border cash flow.
Azam and Gavrilu [80]	1982-2015	The study indicates that growth foreign cash flow is important to make the financial activity more efficient, thus indicating a positive relationship between foreign cash flow and financial efficiency.

III. Data and Methodology of the study

The study considered panel data, consist of a sample of 46 countries representing the period spanning 2004-2018, for empirical estimation. The selection of countries and study period significantly relies on data availability, especially data about financial inclusion. All the data were extracted from the World development indicator (WDI) published by World Bank and the international financial statistics (IFS) published by International Monetary Fund. Data were converted in the natural log before empirical estimation[86].

Financial inclusion

Financial inclusion can be defined as the related availability and the easiness of the financial service to everyone. IT concludes pectoral proceeds where individuals and other businesses can interfere with appropriate, affordable, and timely financial products and services. These include banking, loan, equity, and insurance products. Financial inclusion vastly looks at unbanked, underbanked and directs sustainable financial services to them. The financial inclusion system also determined the fact related to the banking system and other valuable financial services. Various bank financial institutions can categorize the policy to increase the clean image of financial inclusion. Having more inclusive financial systems has been linked to stronger and more sustainable economic growth and development, and thus achieving financial inclusion has become a priority for many countries across the globe. Financial inclusion was popular after the 2000 era when the World Bank shows the importance of financial service to develop the country's economic system and other important factors. The UN defines financial inclusion as the easiness of financial service to use the financial activity in day-to-day work with the maximum reliable sources. Financial inclusion also defines how to use financial activity and any activities that can be done with financial performance.

Financial Inclusion Proxy and reference table

Proxy	Reference
No. of bank ATM per 1000 sq. km.	Morgan and Pontines [37] ; Sarma and Pais [23] ; Zweddu [22] ; Qamruzzaman and Karim [87]
Number of deposit per 1000 people	Bruno and Shin [38] ; Zweddu [22] ; Ackah and Asiamah [40] ; Ramasamy and Yeung [24] ; Qamruzzaman and Wei [88]
No. of branch per 100000 people	Sarma [39] ; Zweddu [22]

No of branch /1000 sq. km.	Mwilima and Institute [42] ; Barrell and Pain [28] ;
No. of bank ATM per 100000 people	Zweddu [22] ; Bevan, Estrin [25] ; Moshirian and Finance [45]

Financial efficiency

Measuring financial efficiency in literature, two-line of thoughts were available that is one group of researchers establish proxy measures considering firms' specific attributes, including Return on investment [31], Per capita income Rate [83], Investment, input/ return, output Ratio [80] and so on. Financial efficiency can be defined as the preferable way to use the financial recourses more precisely if we say the financial activity's output will be more than the input. Financial efficacy is desirable in all organizations of the individual mission. It shows the intensity with which a firm uses and clarifies it to generate gross revenue and the effectiveness of producing, purchasing, pricing, financing, and marketing decisions. At the micro level financial efficiency refers to the efficiency with which resources are correctly allocated among competing uses at a point of time. Financial efficiency is a measure of how well an organization has managed certain trade of (risk and return, liquidity and profitability) in the use of its financial efficiency.

The second line of study considered financial efficiency in terms of aggregated economic aspects. From a theoretical perspective, financial penetration through access to financial services allows a higher degree of economic resource mobilization and reallocation into productive areas [89-91]. Furthermore, In the study of [King and Levine \[92\]](#) and [Sánchez-Robles \[93\]](#) considered M4/GDP as a proxy for financial efficiency in their respective study. Following the motivation of existing literature, the present study follows the same line of estimation.

Foreign capital flows

Foreign capital flows involve capital flows from one country to another, granting the foreign investors extensive ownership stakes in domestic companies and assets or remittance send from another country or even aid from another country. Foreign investment denotes that foreigners have an active role in management as a part of their investment or an equity stake large enough to enable the foreign investor to influence business strategy.

FCF Proxy and reference table

Proxy	Reference
FDI	Morgan and Pontines [26] ; Toxopeus and Lensink [20] ; Schoeman, NJ [43] ; Mwilima and Institute [42] ;
Remittance	Toxopeus and Lensink [20] ; Brafu-Insaidoo and Biekpe [52] ; Barrell and Pain [28] ; Athreye and Kapur [41]

Bases on the study motivation and existing literature, the generalized empirical equation can be represented in the following ways

$$FCF^* = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 FI_{it} + \beta_2 FE_{it} + \beta_3 R_i^* + \omega_{it} \quad (1)$$

FCF stands for foreign capital flows proxy by remittance and foreign direct investment in the economy; FI denotes financial inclusion; FE specifies financial efficiency and R* for the equation's list of control variables. The coefficient of $\beta_1 \dots \dots \beta_3$ explain the long-run magnitude is running in the empirical model.

Empirical model estimation initiated following [Pesaran, Shin \[95\]](#) is known as pooled roped Mean hereafter PGM. PGM is capable of estimating both long-run and short-run magnitude with addressing heterogeneity issues. The following ARDL (p, q ...n) as an empirical structure:

$$FCF_{it} = \epsilon_{it} + \sum_{j=1}^p \beta_{ij} FCF_{i,t-j} + \sum_{j=0}^q \gamma_{ij} R_{i,t-j} + \epsilon_{it} \quad (2)$$

Where,

$$\epsilon_{it} = \omega'_t Q_t + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (3)$$

$$R_{i,t-j} = \alpha_i + \beta_{ij} FCF_{i,t-j} + \omega'_t Q_t + \mu_{it} \quad (4)$$

Where y_{it} positions of the dependent variable for sample I , R_{ij} denoted explanatory variable for the group I , and γ_{ij} embodies the factors of explanatory variables, the sample denoted by $i=1,2,\dots,N$, and time by $t=1,2,\dots,T$, whereas, μ_i specifies fixed effects in the equation.

[Pesaran and Smith \[96\]](#) and [Pesaran, Shin \[95\]](#) suggested that ARDL can derive a stable and consistent estimation given that error residuals are not cross-sectional dependence. Furthermore, the integration variables' order is not an essential factor in assessment [\[97-99\]](#). Besides, the ARDL procedure recognizes short-and since quite a while ago run elements of the model, through an unhindered blunder rectification model (ECM), got from the fundamental ARDL relapse. More explicitly, an ECM specification of Eq. (2) given

Following [Pesaran, Shin \[95\]](#), The generalized empirical ARDL model for investigating the long-run association between trade openness is as follows

$$\Delta FCF_{it} = \alpha_i + \xi_i (FI_{it-1} - FE_{it-1} - \omega'_t R_{it-1}) + \sum_{j=1}^{M-1} \gamma_{ij} \Delta FI_{it-j} + \sum_{j=0}^{N-1} \beta_{ij} \Delta R_{it-j} + \mu_{it} \quad (5)$$

Where $\xi_i = -1(1 - \sum_{j=1}^M \gamma_{ij})$, $\omega'_t = \xi_i^{-1} \sum_{j=0}^N \beta_{ij}$, $\gamma_{i,j}^* = -\sum_{l=j+1}^M \gamma_{il}$ for $J=1, 2, \dots, M-1$, and $\beta_{i,j}^* = -\sum_{l=j+1}^N \beta_{il}$ For $J=1, 2, \dots, N-1$. ($EQ_{it-1} - \omega'_t X_{it-1}$) Specify the long-run relationship between trade openness and independent variables in the equation. At the same time, the term ω_i is a vector of long-run elasticity. ξ_i represents the speed of the dependent variable to changes in the forcing variables. The coefficient of ECT is expected to be negative in signed and statistically significant if the variables covered in the long-run equilibrium. Furthermore, in Equation (5), the short-run dynamics represent by $\gamma_{i,j}^*$, β_{ij}^*

Cross-sectional ARDL

Note, nonetheless, and panel ARDL undertakes errors are cross-sectionally independent. Nevertheless, In some situations, such perceived notions might produce spurious estimation and lead to badly predisposed estimates if the regressors' unobserved common factors correlated. [Chudik and Pesaran \[100\]](#) propose implementing the [Pesaran \[101\]](#) Common Correlated Effects (CCE) approach in the context of panel ARDL models. [Pesaran \[101\]](#) displays the average values used in the equation to represent unobserved common factors as a proxy of dependent and independent variables. Therefore, when averaging equations (2) and (3) across *time*, we obtain

$$\overline{FCF}_{it} = \bar{\alpha}_{it} + \sum_{j=1}^p \bar{\beta}_{ij} \overline{FCF}_{i,t-j} + \sum_{j=0}^q \bar{\gamma}_{ij} \bar{R}_{i,t-j} + \bar{\omega}'_t Q_t + \bar{\epsilon}_{it} \quad (6)$$

$$\text{Where, } \bar{\alpha}_{it} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N \alpha_i}{N}$$

$$\overline{FCF}_{t-j} = \frac{\sum_i FCF_{i,t-j}}{N}, \quad \bar{\gamma}_j = \frac{\sum_i \gamma_{i,j}}{N}, \quad j = 0,1,2 \quad p$$

$$\bar{R}_{t-j} = \frac{\sum_i R_{i,t-j}}{N}, \quad \bar{\gamma}_j = \frac{\sum_i \gamma_{i,j}}{N}, \quad j = 0,1,2 \quad q$$

$$\bar{\omega}_j = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N \omega_i}{N}, \bar{\epsilon}_t = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N \epsilon_{i,t}}{N}$$

The error term, ϵ_i , in Eq. (6) is independently distributed across time and countries, mean congregates to zero (i.e., $\bar{\epsilon}_t = 0$) in root mean square error as $N \rightarrow \infty$. Therefore, the linear effects of both dependent and independents can establish in the presence of cross-sectional dependence in μ_i ,

$$\begin{aligned} FCF_{it} &= \bar{\alpha}_{it} + \sum_{j=1}^p \bar{\Psi}_{ij} \overline{FCF}_{i,t-j} + \sum_{j=0}^q \bar{\gamma}_{ij} \bar{R}_{i,t-j} + \bar{\omega}'_t Q_t \quad (7) \\ &\quad \downarrow \\ \bar{\omega}'_t Q_t &= \overline{FCF}_{it} - \bar{\alpha}_{it} + \sum_{j=1}^p \bar{\Psi}_{ij} \overline{FCF}_{i,t-j} + \sum_{j=0}^q \bar{\gamma}_{ij} \bar{R}_{i,t-j} \\ &\quad \downarrow \\ G_t &= \overline{FCF}_{it} - \bar{\alpha}_{it} + \sum_{j=1}^p \bar{\Psi}_{ij} \overline{FCF}_{i,t-j} + \sum_{j=0}^q \bar{\gamma}_{ij} \bar{R}_{i,t-j} / \bar{\omega}'_t \end{aligned}$$

Thus, the Panel CS-ARDL specification of equation (2)

$$FCF_{it} = \epsilon_{it} + \sum_{j=1}^p \Psi_{ij} \overline{FCF}_{i,t-j} + \sum_{j=0}^q \gamma_{ij} \bar{R}_{i,t-j} + \sum_{j=0}^p \bar{\delta}'_{tj} \bar{Q}_{i,t-j} + \epsilon_{it} \quad (8)$$

Where $\bar{Q} = (\overline{FDI}, \bar{X})$ and $S_{\bar{Z}}$ in the number of lagged cross-sectional average furthermore, equation (8) can be reparametrized to the effects of ECM presentation of Panel CS-ARDL as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta FCF_{it} &= \alpha_i + \xi_i (FCF_{it-1} - \omega'_t R_{it-1}) + \sum_{j=1}^{M-1} \gamma_{ij} \Delta FCF_{i,t-j} + \sum_{j=0}^{N-1} \beta_{ij} \Delta R_{i,t-j} + \sum_{j=1}^p \lambda_j \overline{\Delta FCF}_{i,t-j} \\ &\quad + \sum_{j=0}^q \delta_j \overline{\Delta R}_{i,t-j} + \sum_{j=0}^{S_{\bar{Z}}} \bar{\delta}'_{tj} \bar{Q}_{i,t-j} + \mu_{it} \quad (9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Where } \overline{\Delta FCF}_{t-j} = \frac{\sum_i \Delta FCF_{i,t-j}}{N}, \overline{\Delta R}_{t-j} = \frac{\sum_i \Delta R_{i,t-j}}{N}$$

IV. Model estimation and interpretation

4.1 Unit root test, homogeneity test and cross-sectional dependency test

In the cross-sectional dependency test, we value all four tests Breusch-Pagan LM [102], Pesaran scaled LM, Bias-corrected scaled LM, Pesaran CD; all values of test variables are significant. Among the four cross-sectional dependency tests, there is a cross-sectional relationship between all variables. That means each variable influence or help to conclude other value. All six variables influence able with each other. They are not isolated; each one influences the other. Each and every variable data seems significant, which means we can confirm that the data and the variable we are taking for tests are cross-sectionally dependent on each other they are confront influencing each other.

In addition to C`DS, in the following section, the study intends to evaluate heterogeneity following the framework familiarized by [Pesaran and Yamagata \[103\]](#). The estimation results display in **Error! Reference source not found.** with two coefficients, i.e., Δ and adj Δ . Study findings establish the availability of

heterogeneous properties in the selected data set by rejecting the null hypothesis of homogeneity at a 1% level of significance

Table I Cross-sectional dependency and Heterogeneity test

	Breusch-Pagan LM	Pesaran scaled LM	Bias-corrected scaled LM	Pesaran CD	Δ	Adj. Δ
BC	740.4731***	43.851***	43.539***	22.378***	25.261***	74.487***
FDI	6448.494***	108.717***	108.160***	56.445***	78.55***	56.044***
CBB	4002.898***	268.980***	268.810***	63.183***	65.459***	78.137***
R	21648.55***	422.136***	421.524***	138.662***	22.281***	141.457***
DCP	23734.50***	465.148***	464.591***	146.647***	42.274***	74.13***
M	25843.08***	508.626***	508.069***	156.614***	37.209***	54.608***

The study then moves to determine the order of integration variables by performing several panel unit root tests. The results of the first-generation unit root test displays in Table II. study findings reveal that variables are integrated in mixed order; that is, few variables are stationary at a level, and few become stationary after first difference I(1). Moreover, no variables are exposed to stationary after the second difference.

Table II First-generation Panel unit root test

	Levin, Lin & Chu t*	IPS W-stat	ADF - Fisher Chi	PP - Fisher Chi-square	Breitung t-stat	Hadri Z-stat
R	239.394	5.24827	152.280	315.890	-0.54591	2.20112
Δ R	0.12570	-2.283**	217.435***	3835.22***	-3.786***	2.836**
FDI	-15.5998	-19.404***	584.051	1244.39	-10.2936	2.74097
Δ FDI	5.84571	-16.560***	880.023***	9504.82***	-6.148***	14.733***
CBB	-2.60480	-5.08789	90.3301	265.226	-2.57564	-0.12787
Δ CBB	-2.220**	-14.526***	250.312***	2505.52***	-1.885**	1.747**
DCP	2.18820	-1.15424	39.5041	150.450	-1.99779	0.12268
Δ DCP	-23.301***	-16.059***	598.562***	4946.87***	0.28691	2.311**
BC	-25.4753	-5.21539	95.8755	98.4548	-2.58981	2.09655
Δ BC	-14.050***	-6.884***	28.411***	33.051***	-0.333**	18.100***
M	7.75689	-4.26385	203.635	870.582	-0.38257	-1.15437
Δ M	-11.179***	-14.4402***	583.685***	7680.74***	-5.489***	8.263***

Note: ***/**, denotes the level of significant at a 10%/5/1%, respectively. Δ specify first difference operation

Furthermore, the study performed a second-generation unit root test initiated by Pesaran [104] and can handle cross-sectional dependency. The results of second-generation unit-roots display in Table III. It apparent from estimation that variables are stationary in mixed order, indicating that variables are stationary either at the level or/and after the first difference. Moreover, no variables expose stationary after 2nd difference, which is desirable in empirical estimation.

Table III Second generation Unit root test

	CIPS				CADF			
	At level		Δ		At level		Δ	
	C	C&T	C	C&T	C	C&T	C	C&T
BC	-2.213	-2.594***	-7.016***	-3.189***	-1.256	-1.706	-5.599***	-5.059***

FDI	-2.443	-2.591***	-3.27***	-7.468***	-1.023	-1.907	-4.363***	-7.984***
CBB	-2.647***	-1.944	-6.456***	-6.848***	-1.268	-2.462***	-6.869***	-3.046***
R	-1.997	-1.275	-5.772***	-4.751***	-1.399	-1.396	-4.861***	-6.922***
DCP	-2.253	-1.975	-6.503***	-7.152***	-1.706	-1.822	-5.379***	-3.902***
M	-2.163	-2.677	-2.889***	-2.425	-1.052	-2.326	-6.923***	-2.976***

Note: */**/***, denotes the level of significant at a 10%/5/1%, respectively. Δ specify first difference operation

For a long-run association in the empirical equation, the study move to perform a panel cointegration test initiated by [Pedroni \[105\]](#) and further developed by [Pedroni \[106\]](#) and [Kao \[107\]](#). The results of the Pedroni cointegration test displays in Panel – A of Table IV. It is obvious that out of eleven (11) test statistics, most test statistics are statistically significant at a 1% level, indicating the obvious long-run association between financial inclusion, financial efficiency and inflows of foreign capital in the economy. The verdict of long-run association valid for all four (04) tested models.

Furthermore, the results of Kao cointegration display in Panel-B of Table IV. The test statistics are statistically significant at a 1% level of significance, implying the null hypothesis's rejection. Thus we can conclude that the long-run relationship between financial inclusion, financial efficiency and foreign capital flows in the economy.

Table IV Cointegration test

	[1]	[2]	[3]	[4]
Panel-A: Padroni Cointegration test				
Panel v-Statistic	-3.197	-4.408	1.347*	1.029
Panel rho-Statistic	-6.679***	-2.175**	-1.881**	-2.426***
Panel PP-Statistic	-14.486***	-8.639**	-8.060***	-7.721***
Panel ADF-Statistic	-3.280***	-11.630***	-1.440*	0.758
Group rho-Statistic	-3.143***	-4.868***	-0.356	-4.332***
Group PP-Statistic	-13.496***	12.023	-8.103***	-6.920***
Group ADF-Statistic	-0.742	19.350	-0.097	1.571
Panel v-Statistic	-3.522	-4.852	-0.553	0.995
Panel rho-Statistic	-4.382***	-5.883***	-2.243**	-2.054**
Panel PP-Statistic	-12.354***	-11.625***	-10.074***	-6.213***
Panel ADF-Statistic	-3.290***	-13.656***	-1.313*	-1.016*
Panel-B: ADF - Cointegration test				
Kao test	2.900***	5.528***	-3.068***	-10.659***

Other than the conventional panel cointegration test, the study performs error correction based panel cointegration proposed by [Westerlund \[108\]](#) and results display in Table V. Study findings ascertain the presence of a long-run association between financial inclusion, financial efficiency and foreign capital flows in the economy.

Table V Results of Westerlund panel cointegration test

	[1]		[2]		[3]		[4]	
Test	Value	Z-Value	Value	Z-Value	Value	Z-Value	Value	Z-Value
Group-T	-4.315***	-4.509	-5.214***	-4.509	-4.224**	-1.141	-7.224***	-1.411
Group- α	-9.258 ***	9.991	-9.258 ***	9.991	-5.451 ***	6.774	-4.772 **	4.667
Panel-T	-22.31***	-7.076	-17.211***	-7.076	-10.554***	-7.341	-14.774***	-5.117

Panel- α	-7.327 ***	-1.223	-5.321 ***	-1.223	-4.244 **	-0.475	-5.666 ***	-0.572
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Note: ***/**/* shows the rejection of the null hypothesis at a level of 1%, 5%, & 10%.

4.2 Baseline estimation with OLS, RE and FE

Before proceeds with prime empirical model estimation, the study performs baseline model estimation with ordinary Least square (OLS, hereafter), Random effects (RE, hereafter), and Fixed effects (FE). The results of baseline estimation display in Table VI. The test statistics of the Hausman test ascertain the robustness in favor of FE. Results report in column [3] suggested that financial inclusion measuring access to financial services play augmenting role in receiving foreign capital in the form of FDI. Furthermore, banks' access to credit as a proxy of financial inclusion exposes a positive statistically significant tie to foreign capital flows (see column 6). On the other hand, FCF measured by remittances inflow in the economy also established positive lineage with the expansion of financial territory, i.e., easy access to financial services and extension of credit facility in the financial system (see columns 9 & 12).

In terms of financial efficiency impact on FCF, it is apparent that positive motivational forces are running from financial efficiency to FCF in the economy. This finding suggests that operational efficiency in the financial system allows the greater extension to inject foreign cash flows into the economy.

Table VI Baseline estimation: Financial inclusion, financial efficiency and foreign capital inflows

	Dependent Variable: FDI						Dependent Variable: Remittance					
	[1]	[2]	[3]	[4]	[5]	[6]	[7]	[8]	[9]	[10]	[11]	[12]
	OLS	RE	FE	OLS	RE	FE	OLS	RE	FE	OLS	RE	FE
<i>FI1</i>	0.185***	0.132***	0.138***				0.070*	-0.037	-0.049*			
<i>FI2</i>				0.324***	0.251***	0.298***				0.142*	0.155**	0.194***
<i>FE</i>	0.153***	0.116***	0.109***	0.017	0.016	0.011**	-0.034*	0.041*	0.056*	-0.064*	0.226**	0.275**
<i>Y</i>	-0.047	-0.120**	-0.092*	-0.150***	-0.159*	-0.162*	0.048*	0.102**	0.110*	-0.021	-0.009	-0.035
<i>TO</i>	0.0387***	0.032***	0.035***	0.029***	0.028***	0.028***	0.062***	0.074***	0.073***	-0.019	0.017	-0.014
<i>DCP</i>	-0.136***	-0.117***	-0.116***	-0.066***	-0.071**	-0.062*	-0.047*	-0.088**	-0.101**	0.087***	0.088***	0.090***
<i>GCF</i>	-0.052	-0.046**	-0.065***	-0.052*	-0.069*	-0.054*	0.077**	0.153***	0.137***	-0.040*	-0.024	0.003
<i>C</i>	-	2.375***	2.749***	-	1.425195	0.589	-	-4.089***	-3.844***	0.005	0.094*	0.123**
H-test			0.245			0.754			0.487			0.884

ARDL and CS-ARDL estimation

The following section deals with assessing both long-run and short-run effects running from financial inclusion, financial efficiency to foreign capital flows in road and belt countries by performing both ARDL and CS-ARDL. The empirical model estimation results are reported in Table VII.

Results in column [1-2] with financial inclusion which depositors in commercial banks measure. It is manifested that a positive statistically significant association with foreign capital flows in the economy (a coefficient of 0.313) for ARDL estimation and (a coefficient of 0.185) with CS-ARDL estimation. These findings suggest that access to formal banking services entices home countries population working in different countries to send money to the economy in remittances. Furthermore, the results are in columns [3-4] with financial inclusion measured by commercial banks' borrowers. The study reveals that the extension of credit facilities to the economy also triggered remittances inflows. The positive linkage established in both estimations is ARDL (a coefficient of 0.073) and CS-ARDL (a coefficient of 0.124). These findings in line with existing literature [Qamruzzaman, Jianguo \[109\]](#); [Ajefu and Ogebe \[110\]](#); [Anzoategui, Demirgüç-Kunt \[111\]](#). It is apparent that inclusion into the formal financial system through credit and

service extension impresses a positive note in the mind of remittances earner and eventually encourages them to send home country. In a study [Chuc, Li \[112\]](#) advocated that enabling an inclusive finance market and that the unbanked population is advised to increase the positive effect of remittances on economic development. It includes inducing money transfer recipients to use financial products to promote unnecessary provision, but supplying financial products without utilizing them may be inefficient. In low-income countries, this strategy is particularly recommended, and the inclusion of a larger and more efficient financial structure empowers refugees to return funds to their home countries and allows citizens in their countries of residence to invest their money in banks[\[113\]](#). The establishment of financial institutions in the receiving country may increase the flow of financial services into the sending country, enabling more people to access credit and savings products[\[114\]](#).

Refers to the nexus between financial efficiency and remittances inflows in the economy. Study findings reveal that the positive statistically significant possessions are running from financial efficiency to FCF in all panel estimation. This finding indicates that the positive growth in the degree of financial efficiency can result in foreign remittances from migrants in different countries. [Paul, Barnabé \[115\]](#) postulate that migrants in developed countries return money home to their families to gain further income. To help with this, developing countries that collect money from migrants can increase their financial performance, which is one aspect of financial growth. Reducing the volume of money sent through the informal channel will lead to smaller sums being transmitted through the formal channel.

For the short-run assessment, the error correction terms' coefficient is negative statistically significant at a 1% level. It suggests the presence of long-run convergence due to prior period shocks in short at speed from 15.4% to 54.1%. Furthermore, concerning magnitudes of financial inclusion and financial efficiency on FCF, the sign of the coefficients are in line with the long-run, but in terms of elasticities, it is obvious that minimal effects are running towards remittances inflow in the economy.

Table VII ADRL and CS-ARDL (Dependent variable: Remittance)

	ARDL	CS-ARDL	ARDL	CS-ARDL
Panel –A: Long-run coefficients				
FI ¹	0.313 [22.141]***	0.185[25.145]***	-	-
FI ²	-	-	0.073[15.471]***	0.124[25.745]***
FE	0.082[45.774]**	0.153[25.441]***	0.080[12.411]**	0.017[17.445]***
Y	0.197[17.845]**	0.047[11.541]*	0.069[5.745]*	0.150[8.745]*
TO	0.029[22.745]***	0.038[12.774]***	0.049[55.745]***	0.029[12.445]***
FD	0.012[-0.041]	0.136[14.774]***	0.003[0.554]	0.066[8.447]**
GCF	0.063*[8.744]	0.045[45.441]***	0.055[9.447]*	-0.052[-11.855]*
Panel-B: Short-run coefficients				
ζ_{it}	-0.493[]***	-0.514[-14.744]**	-0.360 [-15.414]***	-0.154[-45.784]***
ΔFI^1	0.049[4.755]*	0.015***[14.754]		
ΔFI^2			0.048[5.211]**	0.015[14.251]*
ΔFE	0.034[8.774]*	0.022[0.845]	-0.027[-17.452]*	0.071 [9.774]***
ΔY	-0.03[-0.14]	0.041[8.774]**	0.091[8.441]***	0.051[6.117]*
ΔTO	0.030[4.511]***	0.041[5.786]*	0.006[0.144]	0.007[24.441]**
ΔFD	-0.057[-14.774]***	0.044[14.541]***	-0.022[-10.554]***	0.074[15.745]**

Δ GCF	-0.093[-4.751]***	0.074[22.451]*	-0.010[-14.21]***	0.074[10.771]*
H test (p-value)	0.561	0.331	0.745	0.887
CD test		11.07		16.291

Note: ***/**/* specify the level of significance at a 1%/5%/10%, respectively. The values with [] for std-error of each coefficient

Next, we gauge the impact of financial inclusion and financial efficiency on FCF, measured by inflows of FDI in the economy by implementing ARDL and AC-ARDL. The results of empirical estimation display in Table VIII. In the long-run, the impact of financial inclusion measured by access to formal financial services positively assists in receiving continual inflows of FCF in the form of FDI (a coefficient of 0.16) in ARDL estimation and (a coefficient of 0.112) in CS-ARDL, see column [1] and [2]. Besides, financial inclusion measured by access to credit services in the financial system established a positive tie with foreign direct investment in the economy with the model estimation ARDL (a coefficient of 0.052) and CS-ARDL (a coefficient of 0.098), see Column [3] and [4]. It is in line with [116-118]. Study findings suggest that financial accessibility predominately guides the persistence in receiving foreign investment in the people's economy. In the study of [Rjoub, Aga \[119\]](#), they advocated that the inflows of FDI immensely rely on country-specific attributes. The functional financial accessibility triggers the growth of FDI inflows in the economy. [Levine \[7\]](#) postulated that a lower degree of financial intermediation could produce undesirable effects on FDI inflows in the economy due to the inefficient domestic financial sector and its attraction among foreign investors.

Refers to the association between financial efficiency and inflows of FDI, it is apparent that positive effects are running between them, and this verdict is available in all empirical estimation. It is in the line with [Alfaro, Chanda \[120\]](#); [Buch, Kesternich \[121\]](#); [Kandilov, Leblebicioğlu \[122\]](#). Study findings suggest that foreign investment inflows are immensely influenced by efficiency financial intermediation and operational efficiency in the long-run financial sector. Furthermore, [Xu \[123\]](#) suggests that a lower degree of financial intermediation diminishes the beneficial effects of FDI in the economy, thus discouraging foreign investors from channelizing funds into those countries.

Results of short-run model estimation display in Panel-B of Table VIII. The coefficients of error correction terms are negative and statistically significant at a 1% level of significance. It is indicating that the presence of long-run convergence in the equation. The impact of financial inclusion on FDI exposes a positive statistically significant either 1% or 5% level of significance; albite their elasticities are minimal compared to long-run estimation. On the other hand, financial efficiency exposes a positive, statistically significant bond with inflows of FDIs in the economy.

Table VIII Results of ADRL and CS-ARDL (Dependent variable: FDI)

	ARDL	CS-ARDL	ARDL	CS-ARDL
	[1]	[2]	[3]	[4]
<i>Panel-A: Long-run coefficients</i>				
FI ¹	0.146[45.845]***	0.112[24.512]***		
FI ²			0.052[14.221]***	0.098[15.231]***
FE	0.013[15.415]**	0.051[10.214]**	0.032[41.551]	0.074[14.210]**
Y	0.054[5.775]*	0.074[9.124]**	0.052[16.524]**	0.120[12.512]***
TO	0.033[23.775]***	0.0845[14.52]***	0.017[45.521]**	0.041[14.551]***
FD	0.072[9.114]*	0.075[25.441]***	0.033[45.114]***	0.0541[25.415]***
GCF	-0.101[-15.241]***	0.014[45.254]***	-0.028[-15.741]**	0.045[14.591]***

ζ_{it}	-0.882[-45.714]***	-0.554[-75.214]***	-0.432[-12.451]***	-0.445[95.124]***
ΔFI^1	0.029[9.151]*	0.004[12.541]**		
ΔFI^2			0.016[14.715]*	0.054[14.612]**
ΔFE	0.012[22.511]**	0.005[8.021]*	-0.048[-12.745]	0.011[45.712]**
ΔY	-0.015[-15.120]**	-0.059[10.845]*	0.008[25.774]***	0.015[12.445]**
ΔTO	-0.028[12.331]	0.002[5.214]*	0.070[7.841]*	0.051[25.125]***
ΔFD	0.012[25.314]***	0.008[5.218]*	-0.030[28.941]***	0.081[8.215]***
ΔGCF	0.047[10.254]***	0.055[7.94]*	0.088[10.228]**	0.005[9.351]**
H test (p-value)	0.541	0.145	0.661	0.254
CD test		45.751		78.251

Note: ***/**/* specify the level of significance at a 1%/5%/10#, respectively. The values with [] for std-error of each coefficient

Next, the study moves to assess the robustness in empirical estimation by implementing GMM and system GMM estimation. Results of robustness estimation display in Table IX.

Estimation with GMM, results display in column [1]-[4]. Considering the nexus between financial inclusion and foreign capital flows proxy by remittances in the equation. It is apparent that a positive, statistically significant impact running between them, which is true in all four model outcomes, see column [1-4]. These findings suggest that remittance inflows in the economy can be augmented by expediting financial inclusion by offering financial services and product diversifications in the financial system. The impact of financial efficiency on remittances inflow also divulges positive association, implying that the financial system's degree of efficiency acts as a motivational factor in encouraging the inflows of remittances in the economy. Furthermore, System-GMM estimation for financial efficiency and FCF in the form of FDI, see Column [5-8], exposes a positive statistically significant relationship, which is available in both proxy measures in financial inclusion the equation. These findings suggest that access to financial service acts as a boosting factor in augmenting foreign capital inflows in the economy in either form.

While the impact of financial efficiency and foreign capital flows under both model estimation, it is obvious that positive effects running from financial efficiency to FCF in all eight estimations. This suggests that efficient financial intermediation and affecting mobilization of economic resources in the economy can increase the inflows of FCF in the economy as a catalyst to motivate foreign investors and migrant's residence.

Table IX GMM and system GMM estimation

	GMM-estimation				System-GMM estimation			
	[1]	[2]	[3]	[4]	[5]	[6]	[7]	[8]
$X^*(-1)$	-	-	-	-	0.258*	0.803***	0.351***	0.868***
FI^1	0.185***	0.070*	-	-	0.179***	0.007	-	-
FI^2	-	-	0.324***	0.064*	-	-	0.591**	0.029***
FE	0.153***	0.034*	0.017***	0.021**	0.173***	0.008*	0.039**	0.071**
Y	-0.047*	0.048*	-0.150*	-0.019	-0.112*	0.020*	0.137**	0.002*
TO	0.038***	0.062***	0.029***	0.087***	0.026*	0.014***	-0.067	0.011***
FD	-0.136***	0.047*	0.066**	0.040*	-0.121***	-0.017**	0.167	0.003
GCF	-0.005	0.077**	-0.052*	0.005	-0.031*	0.030***	0.163	0.012**

AR1 (p-value)	0.000	0.001	0.001	0.000	0.002	0.000	0.000	0.000
AR2 (p-value)	0.867	0.745	0.445	0.741	0.274	0.884	0.914	0.426
Sargan (p-value)	0.500	0.451	0.551	0.751	0.551	0.265	0.441	0.41

Note: ***/**/* indicates the level of significant at a 1%/5%/10%, respectively

The following section deals with assessing the granger causality test with the non-granger causality test proposed by [Toda and Yamamoto \[124\]](#) in the panel form. The results of the causality test display in Table X consist of four-panel of the outcome, i.e., Panel – A with FCF measured by remittances and financial inclusion measure by access to financial services; panel-B with financial inclusion proxied by access to credit facilities; Panel-C and Panel –D with FCF measured by inflows of foreign direct investment in respective equations. Study findings disclosed several causal associations in their estimation; however, the study intends to gauge the prime motivation: financial inclusion, financial efficiency, and foreign capital flow in the economy.

Study findings reveal bidirectional causality between financial inclusion and foreign capital inflows in the form of remittances [FI $\leftrightarrow$ R] and financial efficiency and remittances [FE $\leftrightarrow$ R], see panel –A, and financial efficiency and FCF in the form of FDI [FE $\leftrightarrow$ FDI], see Panel-D. Study findings in line with [Qamruzzaman and Wei \[125\]](#); [Odugbesan, Ike \[126\]](#); [Agbloyor, Abor \[127\]](#). Better financial markets allow agents in the economy to take advantage of knowledge spillovers from FDI[128]. Furthermore, unidirectional causality runs from financial inclusion and financial efficiency to FCF, and these verdicts are applicable in the rest of the causal assessment in the estimation.

Table X Results of Causality test following Toda-Yamamoto

	FCF	FI	FE	Y	TO	DCP	GCF
Panel-A: Dependent variable FCF measured by Remittances							
FCF	-	13.024***	33.417***	2.5123*	20.070***	17.484***	3.127*
FI	18.629***	-	29.202***	1.400	20.546***	26.980***	1.545
FE	3.305*	62.588***	-	3.123*	9.444**	6.285**	7.0276**
Y	4.477*	4.681*	0.949	-	0.967	2.166	3.940*
TO	38.979***	9.419**	2.070	2.248	-	13.870***	10.927***
FD	0.067	73.662***	4.544*	3.812*	4.197*	-	13.940***
GCF	16.320***	4.062*	3.827*	1.462	7.209**	8.451**	-
Panel-B: Dependent variable FCF measured by Remittances							
FCF	-	62.914***	5.440*	8.544*	113.576***	4.949*	7.714**
FI	1.903	-	1.769	0.216	6.529**	11.155***	7.564**
FE	1.283	166.757***	-	1.740	3.576*	7.690**	8.669**
Y	3.797*	6.623**	8.823**	-	7.020**	11.679***	7.448**
TO	71.175***	102.561***	1.631	15.456***	-	29.071***	2.206
FD	9.909***	115.731***	2.760*	3.262*	3.179*	-	17.523***
GCF	18.984***	52.140***	16.448***	4.942*	9.178**	7.803**	-
Panel-C: Dependent variable FCF measured by Foreign Direct Investment							
FCF	-	1.910	2.161	0.197	23.339***	11.976***	13.480***
FI	1.935	-	22.854***	3.294**	6.989**	26.438***	1.813
FE	4.595*	35.424***	-	2.137	2.290	4.165*	8.229**
Y	7.454**	32.536***	10.747***	-	0.566	18.926***	0.858
TO	3.791*	14.080***	4.546*	0.610	-	26.119***	16.301***
FD	2.893*	38.240***	5.783*	2.497*	3.587*	-	14.960***

GCF	5.083*	2.730*	6.106**	2.829*	5.536*	36.886***	-
Panel-D: Dependent variable FCF measured by Foreign Direct Investment							
FCF	-	3.109*	1.641*	0.464	36.076***	8.069***	9.352***
FI	1.054	-	25.396***	4.146*	4.916**	29.711***	2.191*
FE	2.619*	38.308***	-	3.545**	1.322	4.818**	19.099***
Y	1.283	3.857*	2.883*	-	0.600	3.172*	2.257*
TO	1.410*	17.456***	1.769*	2.791**	-	9.106***	18.932***
FD	1.946*	35.919***	4.432**	2.385*	3.066*	-	26.752***
GCF	3.657*	5.060**	10.666***	1.394*	7.933***	45.297***	-

Note: ***/**/* indicates the level of significant at 15/55/10%, respectively

V. Conclusion and findings

Cross-broader capital inflows and their deterrents have produced an extensive interest in empirical studies due to unprecedented impacts in every corner of the economy. The present study's motivation is to evaluate the impact of financial inclusion and financial efficiency on foreign capital flows, measured by inflows of FDI and remittance, for the period spanning 1971-2018 in Road and Belts countries. Exposing the association and potential impacts on foreign capital flows from financial inclusion and financial efficiency, the study performed several econometrical techniques, and the summary of empirical findings are as follows:

First, the study began empirical assessment with cross-sectional dependency, the test of heterogeneity, and unit root tests. The results of the cross-sectional dependency test expose internal dependency availability among the units of research variables. Furthermore, the test of heterogeneity ascertains the presence of heterogeneous properties. On the other hand, panel unit root tests with first and second-generation established that variables are stationary either at a level or after the first difference, but neither variables expose stationary after the second difference.

Second, to gauge the long-run association between financial inclusion, financial efficiency and foreign capital flows, the study executes the panel cointegration test following Pedroni [Pedroni \[105\]](#), [Pedroni \[106\]](#) and [Kao \[107\]](#). The associate p-value of test statistics rejected the null hypothesis, i.e., no-cointegration, and established the empirical estimation's long-run association. Furthermore, the study performed a panel cointegration test based on the error correction Model following [Westerlund \[129\]](#) and ascertain the long-run relationship between financial inclusion, financial efficiency, and foreign capital flows.

Third, the empirical output with ARDL and CS-ARDL exposes a positive and statistically significant association between financial inclusion, financial efficiency, and foreign capital inflows in the long-run and short-run economies. These findings suggest that money inflows from external sources in migrants' remittances and foreign direct investment seek easy access to financial services in the formal financial system. Furthermore, the availability of credit benefits can also accelerate the receipts of cash flows from outside of the economy in either form. Thus, it is essential to authorize access to financial services and diversity in credit development to ensure foreign capital's continued inflows in the economy. [Shleifer and Vishny \[130\]](#) argued that financial intermediaries operating efficiency strengthen the oversight of investment operations and promote corporate governance. Due to the presence of business frictions such as high transaction rates and knowledge asymmetries, dispersed shareholders may be discouraged from exercising sufficient influence over funds management.

Fourth, to evaluate directional association, the stud performed a non-granger causality test following Toda [Toda and Yamamoto \[124\]](#) in panel form. Study findings disclosed the feedback hypothesis holds in explaining the causality between financial inclusion and foreign capital inflows in the form of remittances $[FI \leftarrow \rightarrow R]$ and financial efficiency and remittances $[FE \leftarrow \rightarrow R]$, see panel -A, and financial efficiency and FCF in the form of FDI $[FE \leftarrow \rightarrow FDI]$. These findings suggest that the intermediary's role in

the financial system plays a pivotal role in managing the economy's anticipated foreign cash flows and vice-versa.

Financial system performances are critically significant in augmenting financial intermediation, including efficient reallocation of economic resources, financial services diversity, and easy access to the formal financial channel, which positively accelerates the macro and micro fundamental improvement. In terms of capital accumulation and productive investment reallocation, financial efficiency and the degree of unbanked status play a pivotal role and encourage capital flows in the economy, especially from external sources[125]. However, domestic firms' financial constraints negatively cause cash flows to direct foreign investment[131].

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